

Future Internet and Smart City with OpenFlow and Machine Learning - Course Poster

Joberto S. B. Martins

Abstract

Internet and networks are evolving and expanding their utilization dramatically. New paradigms, new protocols, new intelligent solutions and large scale complex systems are emerging on various areas of our daily life. Researchers and engineers need to understand the current network evolution trends and to know what relevant new technologies are involved. This course presents the network evolution scenario and presents the SDN/OpenFlow technology in the context of the actual and challenging Smart City scenario. Smart City characteristics, project issues and development challenges are addressed. SDN/ OpenFlow with some basic Machine Learning tools are applied to Smart City projects to allow a comprehension on how new technologies can improve system development and highlight their potential.

Index Terms

Future Internet, Smart City, Software-defined Networking, OpenFlow, System Development, Machine Learning, Smart City Projects, Cognitive Management.

1 INTRODUCTION

Current communication networks such as 5G, Cloud, IoT (Internet of Things), MPLS and evolutionary systems like Smart City, Smart Grid and Industry 4.0 are marked by a wide variety and large distribution of services, applications, equipment and users alongside with a huge volume of data exchanges with heterogeneous quality assurance requirements (SLA, QoE, QoS) [1] [2] [3].

The evolution of systems and computer networks towards the so called "Future Internet" is being marked by different factors and aspects like:

- The Internet/web continuous expansion and growth in diversity and complexity;
- Network requirements are diverse, ranging from miniaturized interconnect RFID tags and IoT (Internet of Thing) sensor applications to large complex server farms; and
- Users are demanding more intelligent, autonomic, easy-to-use and pervasive applications.

Researchers and engineers are then challenged to develop new technical approaches in terms of network architecture, protocols and intelligent systems to adequately support this new network scenario.

2 COURSE FOCUS

This course focuses on presenting the current network architecture and systems evolutionary trends and explores the Software-defined Networking (SDN) new paradigm as a solution to develop new approaches with a focus on Smart City (Fig. 1) [4] [5].

In technical terms, the course elaborates on two main topics:

- Software-defined Networks (SDN) with OpenFlow; and

-
- *Prof. Dr. Martins, Joberto S. B. is with Salvador University - UNIFACS, Brazil and International Professor at HTW - Hochschule für Technik und Wirtschaft des Saarlandes - Saarbrücken, Germany
E-mail: joberto.martins@gmail.com*

Fig. 1. Course main components view - SDN & Smart City

- Smart City (SC) projects as the application scenario.

A typical Smart City project has most of Future Internet requirements that engineers have to solve like heterogeneity, distributed access points, high volume of data, multiple networks involved and so on [6] [7].

A smart sustainable city is an innovative city that uses information and communication technologies (ICTs) and other means to improve quality of life, efficiency of urban operation and services, and competitiveness, while ensuring that it meets the needs of present and future generations with respect to economic, social and environmental aspects.

Many cities in the world are deploying, planning or considering smart city projects like Saarbrücken initiative and the pioneer Santander smart city project (Figure 2):

- Saarbrücken SC initiative : <https://www.smartcitiesdive.com/ex/sustainablecitiescollective/connectivity-case-study-saarbr-cken-germany/1104149/>
- Santander SC project video : <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=63HB0S72iXw>

Smart City is a quite broad research topic and Smart City projects do address various topics [9] [10]. In terms of this course, the topics discussed will address the following Smart City projects aspects:

- The understanding of the multidisciplinary approach, aspects and technical requirements existing in a Smart City project; and
- The use of SDN/OpenFlow with machine learning to solve typical requirements and needs imposed to the communication layer (Figure 3) of a Smart City project.

A typical Smart City project can be structured as indicated in Figure 3. It has a 3-tier framework with application, communication and devices levels [3].

This course will present firstly how to use SDN/OpenFlow to develop a new, efficient and programmable communications solution (Communication Level) and, secondly, how new techniques like machine learning can be used to allocate resources in a smart city project context (Application Level).

Fig. 2. Saarbrücken towards a Smart City project [8]

The course will explore incrementally the following aspects of system and application development (Figure 4):

- 1) How networks can possibly evolve with SDN and without SDN;
- 2) How SDN supports routing, virtualization and scalability capabilities necessary on current and future systems;
- 3) What are the Smart City issues and requirements for system development;
- 4) How can SDN with cognitive management and machine learning foster new systems development for Smart City; and
- 5) A practical "use case" for Smart City project development.

3 COURSE MOTIVATION

The motivation to follow this course comes from the fact that engineers need to understand what are the main problems that actual IP-based solutions do have, what are the current trends on system development and what are the new technologies to use.

Why to follow this course?

- To learn SDN/OpenFlow basics;
- To experiment SDN/OpenFlow network programming with MiniNet;
- To acquire expertise on Smart City project issues and requirements; and
- To perceive the use of Machine Learning techniques for cognitive management using SDN/OpenFlow as the basic network programming paradigm.

The course is intended for PhD, master and graduate students, network engineers and developers involved with network research, design and implementation. Some basic knowledge of IP and networking technologies is required.

Fig. 3. Smart City Framework View [3]

4 COURSE TOPICS AND HOSTING INSTITUTIONS

The course hosting institutions are:

- HTW - Hochschule für Technik und Wirtschaft des Saarlandes - Saarbrücken, Germany; and
- Salvador University - UNIFACS, Brazil.

The topics presented are (30 hours course):

- 1) Evolutionary Networking Architecture approaches and SDN: (Class n^0 1)
 - Networking evolution scenario
 - Software-Defined Networking (SDN)
 - Networks evolutionary architectural issues: virtualization, cognitive management, autonomy, naming, addressing, mobility, scalability
 - SDN standardization
- 2) SDN/ OpenFlow Protocol Ecosystem: (Classes n^0 2 - 3)
 - OpenFlow (OF) Architecture and EcoSystem
 - OpenFlow and Virtualization
 - OpenFlow Protocol Messages and Flow Diagram
 - OpenFlow Use Cases: virtual router, level 2 virtualization, other
 - OpenFlow hands on with MiniNet:
 - MiniNet and basic OpenFlow operation
 - Virtualization with FlowVisor
- 3) Smart City Project - Characteristics, Requirements and Solutions (Fig. 3): (Class n^0 4)

Fig. 4. Smart City Communications and Machine Learning View

- Smart City Definition, Characteristics and Requirements
- Smart City Framework
- Smart City - Use Cases

4) Smart City Project Use Case: (Class n^0 5)

- Smart City model for network communication
- Data and Internet of Things (IoT) in Smart Cities [11]
- Cognitive Management with Machine Learning (ML) [12] [13]
- Other Smart City technological approaches

Obs.: Reference papers, books, sites, and other online resources will be available at the Moodle support system for all students.

REFERENCES

- [1] F. Theoleyre, T. Watteyne, G. Bianchi, G. Tuna, V. Cagri Gungor, and Ai-Chun Pang. Networking and Communications for Smart Cities Special Issue Editorial. *Computer Communications*, 58:1–3, March 2015.
- [2] R. Bezerra, F. Maristela, and Joberto Martins. On Computational Infraestructure Requirements to Smart and Autonomic Cities Framework. In *IEEE Int. Smart Cities Conference - ISC2-2015*, pages 1–6. IEEE, January 2015.
- [3] Joberto S. B. Martins. Towards Smart City Innovation Under the Perspective of Software-Defined Networking, Artificial Intelligence and Big Data. *Revista de Tecnologia da Informação e Comunicação*, 8(2):1–7, October 2018.
- [4] D. Kreutz, F. M. V. Ramos, P. E. Veríssimo, C. E. Rothenberg, S. Azodolmolky, and S. Uhlig. Software-Defined Networking: A Comprehensive Survey. *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 103(1):14–76, January 2015.
- [5] Subharthi Paul, Jianli Pan, and Raj Jain. Architectures for the Future Networks and the Next Generation Internet: A Survey. *Computer Communications*, 34(1):2–42, January 2011.

-
- [6] A. M. Farid, M. Alshareef, P. S. Badhesha, C. Boccaletti, N. A. A. Cacho, C.-I. Carlier, A. Corriveau, I. Khayal, B. Liner, J. S. B. Martins, F. Rahimi, R. Rossetti, W. C. H. Schoonenberg, A. Stillwell, and Y. Wang. Smart City Drivers and Challenges in Energy and Water Systems. *IEEE Potentials*, 40(1):6–10, January 2021.
 - [7] A. M. Farid, M. Alshareef, P. S. Badhesha, C. Boccaletti, N. A. A. Cacho, C.-I. Carlier, A. Corriveau, I. Khayal, B. Liner, J. S. B. Martins, F. Rahimi, R. Rossetti, W. C. H. Schoonenberg, A. Stillwell, and Y. Wang. Smart City Drivers and Challenges in Urban-Mobility, Health-Care, and Interdependent Infrastructure Systems. *IEEE Potentials*, 40(1):11–16, January 2021.
 - [8] Canin Associates. A Connectivity Case Study in Saarbrücken, Germany, 2021.
 - [9] A. Gharaibeh, M. A. Salahuddin, S. J. Hussini, A. Khreishah, I. Khalil, M. Guizani, and A. Al-Fuqaha. Smart Cities: A Survey on Data Management, Security, and Enabling Technologies. *IEEE Communications Surveys Tutorials*, 19(4):2456–2501, 2017.
 - [10] R. Jalali, K. El-khatib, and C. McGregor. Smart City Architecture for Community Level Services Through the Internet of Things. In *2015 18th Int. Conf. on Intel. in Next Generation Networks*, pages 108–113, February 2015.
 - [11] Carlos E. Arruda, Pedro F. Moraes, Nazim Agoulmine, and Joberto S. B. Martins. Enhanced Pub/Sub Communications for Massive IoT Traffic with SARSA Reinforcement Learning. In *Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Machine Learning for Networking (MLN'2020)*, pages 1–20, Paris, France, November 2020.
 - [12] Eliseu M. Oliveira, Rafael F. Reale, and Joberto S. B. Martins. A Methodological Approach to Model CBR-based Systems. *Journal of Computer and Communications*, 8(9):1–16, September 2020.
 - [13] E. M. Oliveira, R. F. Reale, and J. S. B. Martins. Cognitive Management of Bandwidth Allocation Models with Case-Based Reasoning - Evidences Towards Dynamic BAM Reconfiguration. In *2018 IEEE Symposium on Computers and Communications (ISCC)*, pages 00397–00403, June 2018. ISSN: 1530-1346.

Prof. Dr. Joberto S. B. Martins - Professor at Salvador University (UNIFACS) and PhD in Computer Science at Université Pierre et Marie Curie - UPMC, Paris (1986). Invited Professor at HTW - Hochschule für Technik und Wirtschaft des Saarlandes (Germany) since 2003, Senior Research Period at Université of Paris-Saclay in 2016, Salvador University head and researcher at NUPERC and IPQoS research groups on Resource Allocation Models, Software Defined Networking - OpenFlow, Smart Cities, Smart Grid, Cognitive Management and machine learning application. Previously worked as Invited Professor at Université Paris VI and Institut National des Télécommunications (INT) in France and as key speaker, teacher and invited lecturer in various international congresses and companies in Brazil, US and Europe.